

BEHIND THE ANGEL OF HISTORY THE “ANGELUS NOVUS” AND ITS INTERLEAF

ANNIE BOURNEUF

THE STORY OF ARTIST R. H. QUAYTMAN'S DISCOVERY OF AN ENGRAVING HIDDEN BEHIND A FAMOUS ARTWORK BY PAUL KLEE

This book begins with artist R. H. Quaytman uncovering something startling about a picture by Paul Klee. Pasted beneath Klee's 1920 *Angelus Novus*—famous for its role in the writings of its first owner, Walter Benjamin—Quaytman found that Klee had interleaved a nineteenth-century engraving of Martin Luther, leaving just enough visible to provoke questions.

Behind the Angel of History reveals why this hidden face matters, delving into the intertwined artistic, political, and theological issues consuming Germany in the wake of the Great War. With the *Angelus Novus*, Klee responded to a growing call for a new religious art. For Benjamin, Klee's *Angelus* became bound up with the prospect of meaningful dialogue among religions in Germany.

Reflecting on Klee's, Benjamin's, and Quaytman's strategies of superimposing conflicting images, Annie Bourneuf reveals new dimensions of complexity in this iconic work and the writing it inspired.

“A stunningly brilliant book. *Behind the Angel of History* reads like a detective story; tracing the dialectic undercurrents of a monoprint by Paul Klee, which Bourneuf illuminates with historical nuance, contextualizing Klee's print in the political culture of its time. Bourneuf is to be commended for her prodigious, resourceful scholarship and singular contribution to furthering our understanding of *Angelus novus*.”

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Behind the Angel of History: The “Angelus Novus” and Its Interleaf, The University of Chicago Press

by Annie Bourneuf | August 3, 2022

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